

Research on the Leadership of Subject Leaders in Primary and Secondary Schools

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 24, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: July 24, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Leadership, Management, Teachers' instructional leadership, School Teachers</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6895994</p>	<p><i>Teacher leadership styles are highlighted in this study to help school faculty members. Teachers' instructional leadership duties and personnel or human resource management roles might influence these kinds of leadership. These teacher-respondents confront the requirement to properly encourage teachers in order to guarantee a quality, structured, and stable educational system in the school. Teachers' ability to manage curriculum, teacher resources, educator pedagogies, student accomplishment, and the school's overall academic achievement may all be considered when evaluating these leadership styles. This includes the ability of the instructors to manage and supervise school workers in a way that improves efficiency and effectiveness in the school environment, as well.</i></p>

Introduction

Students and teachers now face several challenges every day, including how to apply the new Common Core State Standards (CCSS), dealing with upset parents, and providing support for burnt-out staff. As instructors, how they respond to these difficulties is critical to their success or failure. Building teachers are expected to be the educational and visionary leaders that every community desires and to effectively manage the day-to-day events that take place in every school building. When it comes to teaching today, these are two of the most challenging and important topics. These two ideas are well-explained in books, yet the impression they convey is often muddled. Getting the organization's job done quickly and effectively is at the top of the priority list for management. Its major emphasis is on getting the task done on a daily basis, which is common for most organizations (Lalonde and Roux-Dufort, 2013).

It's important to remember that leadership concentrates on what has to be done in the future. Achieving one's vision and self-determination are the primary aims of this book. When it comes to getting things done, managers prefer to tell their employees how to do it, whereas leaders look for creative solutions. Management is considered as a method of exerting influence, while leadership is perceived as a means of exerting control. While the manager ensures that all participants stay on track and fulfill their assigned objectives, the leader is always looking for fresh ways to better the situation. Understanding and influencing people's attitudes and the status quo are top priorities for a leader. Stability is advocated by the management, who uses his power to ensure that the objectives are met (Lunenburg, 2011).

The literature on school leadership and management also offers varied viewpoints on the tasks and responsibilities that building instructors must provide (Lunenburg, 2010). Becoming a good building manager isn't enough anymore, that's for sure! As a teacher, you must be a psychologist, a social worker and a school facility manager at the same time. You must also be an evaluation expert and an educational visionary at the same time.

As their tasks get more and more diverse, the demands on them become more fragmented, rapid-fire, and voluminous on a daily basis (Lunenburg, 2010). School or site-based administration, in addition to decentralizing control, has resulted in a shift in the teacher's role, which has resulted in the transfer of a significant amount of decision-making power from the district office to individual schools. Building teachers' jobs have never been more complicated.

As the world becomes more and more complicated, educational leaders must help their institutions adapt to the changes. Many different types of policy directives, such as curriculum standards, achievement benchmarks, programming requirements, and other types of policy directives, result in a tangled web of regulations for educational institutions. There is a growing need for educators to adapt to students' increasingly diverse features, including their cultural background and immigrant status as well as financial inequality and the presence of physical and mental impairments. Managing new cooperation with other child-serving social

organizations is a challenge. Schools' internal operations must be revised in light of the rapid advancements in teaching and communication technology. Some of the factors that make education more difficult and leadership more important include the following: (Leithwood and Riehl, 2003).

Leadership as a concept

Leadership encompasses the capacity of a person or organization to "lead" or "guide" other people, teams, or whole organizations, both theoretically and practically. Western and Eastern approaches to leadership, as well as US and European approaches (within the West) are all debated in the literature. Leadership is defined as "the ability to persuade and motivate people to work together to attain a shared goal," according to academics in the US (Chin, 2015). Leaders use a variety of methods to inspire and guide their employees. The leader's ideology, personality, and experience all have a role in the development of the product. Specialists in rhetorical theory and practice have also devised frameworks for analyzing leadership behavior.

Leadership styles vary depending on the scenario. A more democratic or laissez-faire leadership style may be more successful in a highly motivated and aligned team with a homogenous level of experience, while an authoritarian leadership style may be more effective in an emergency when there is little time to converge on an accord. Adopting a style in which the group's goals are best achieved and the interests of its members are balanced is the ideal approach (Howell, 2008). Military science has lately expressed a holistic and integrated perspective of leadership, including how a leader's physical appearance impacts how others perceive that leader.. Military bearing, physical fitness, self-confidence, and resilience are all variables in physical presence. The ability of a leader to think critically and gather new information is an important part of his or her job. Thinking like a leader requires the ability to move quickly, to make good decisions under pressure and to work well with others. Tactical and technical understanding, as well as cultural and geopolitical sensitivity, is essential for a leader's domain knowledge.

Of course, leadership is a subjective matter. However, its basis is built on the capacity of a person or group to build a following. It's impossible to generalize about the leadership style and approach of everyone. To further complicate matters, each business leader's leadership style and methods will be influenced by a variety of factors, including the modern challenges that all business leaders face today (digitalization; changing regulatory and financial markets; recruiting and retaining talent) as well as predicaments specific to their company, size and industry in which the business is situated (Jennifer, 2017).

Organizational culture and leadership

Various studies have focused on the role of organizational culture and leadership in connection to organizational effectiveness in recent years. Due to the fact that leadership and culture in the workplace are more focused on strategic and development thinking, organizational change may occur more rapidly than in other leadership styles. To this end, Razik (2015) argues that organizational culture and leadership allow the formation of value system congruence between workers and managers, enabling a situation in which both the leader and the followers are motivated to achieve the organization's goals.

- 1) Leaders' directive path-goal-clarification conduct. By providing clear rules, methods, and regulations, as well as scheduling and organizing tasks, this behavior type aims to help subordinates understand what they are expected to accomplish and how they are expected to do it.
- 2) Leaders who exhibit supportive conduct. This style of conduct is oriented toward the needs and preferences of the workers via the expression of care and the building of a supportive and welcoming work environment. Additional benefits include reducing staff stress and alleviating employee discontent when the supporting leader acts as a source of pleasure socially, as well as self-confidence, in this approach.
- 3) Leaders who engage in participative conduct. For example, this form of leadership style encourages employees, runs work units effectively, and influences decision-making by consulting with subordinates and incorporating their opinions.
- 4) A focus on achieving one's goals. This type of behavior is in line with encouraging high levels of performance excellence by identifying areas for improvement, establishing goals that are both challenging and specific, showcasing these achievements, and demonstrating confidence in the ability of the employees to meet those standards.

The teacher's role

Several studies have shown that a school's leadership is the single most significant factor in its effective operation. Teacher leadership responsibilities include: clarifying the school's vision and mission, maintaining a positive working relationship with staff, directing classroom practices, organizing the curriculum and instruction, ensuring that students have the opportunity to learn, and performing in accordance with established standards.

Culbertson (2007) found that democratic leadership is more successful than authoritarian leadership. Every undertaking and difficulty has a human aspect that must be taken into account. Having a moral purpose,

allowing for changing processes, developing reasoning abilities, and being able to maintain consistency in the workplace are all aspects of leadership styles, according to Fullan (2007). A school's educational paradigm can only be changed by a teacher who embodies these traits and refuses to fixate on outmoded systems. Because of this, he thinks that people's leadership styles are deeply ingrained.

Furthermore, McBer (2008) showed that leadership styles are determined by the emotional intelligence of each leader, and include traits such as: being coercive, affiliative, democratic, pace-setting and coaching. When a teacher has these six emotional 25 intelligences, he or she may lead the school with heart instead of only directing teachers like machines.

The study of leadership styles and their ensuing outcomes is an essential part of this investigation. Some of these leadership styles will be briefly examined, as well as the way academics have interpreted their efficacy at work. Transactional leadership may be particularly successful, according to Bass and Avolio (2007).

As Shieh et al. (2008)¹³ put it, "leaders must be aware of the importance of understanding." However, when both transactional and transformational leadership styles are used in tandem, more effort is put forth by those who are led, resulting in improved productivity at work and better levels of job satisfaction among educators.

The school's social atmosphere and its workers' requirements must be taken into consideration.. As a way to address these demands, the transactional leadership style may give positive feedback to employees by rewarding excellent performance. Motivation may be achieved via greater aims rather than immediate self-interest, and for accomplishment and self-actualization instead of security and stability; this kind of leadership is known as transactional leadership (Mendels, 2012). Leaders enable those they lead to become more committed to the school's corporate objectives (Leithwood, 2006).

The six characteristics listed by Goldman (2002) are typical of democratic organizations: policies are determined by a group of organizations; technical and job performance measures are discussed so that they are understood by all; leaders give advice to members on how to carry out tasks; members can choose with whom they work; the group determines the distribution of tasks; and leaders try to be objective when giving praise.

A democratic style of leadership builds agreement via involvement, but these leaders also demand a greater degree of quality and self-direction from their employees. It's been clear to me from my personal experience that these leaders take the time to listen and exchange ideas with their followers. They are also more adaptable and attentive to the demands of the customer. Teacher participation and respect are two of their strongest attributes.

An autocratic leader is likely to have the following characteristics: There is no input from members of the organization when making decisions, the leaders create all policies, the leader decides the methods of work, the leader determines obligations for followers, and the leader specifies technical and performance assessment criteria for the company.

It's possible to make rapid decisions with this kind of leadership since just one person is involved in making the decisions. Despite its unpopularity, the autocratic leadership style has its advantages, particularly when the leader is pressed for time and his or her employees are not productive.

For successful instructors, Turan & Bektas (2013) say that their own conduct influences, motivates, and encourages other teachers. Professional, interpersonal, and personal development are all areas in which teachers seek guidance and assistance from their principals and mentors. As an example, they utilize all of the school's celebration opportunities, such as meetings and ceremonies, to bring together the official and casual components of the school.

In the words of Huang (2011), leaders are capable of increasing and maintaining staff dedication and satisfaction. Every employee, for example, feels the urge to be acknowledged, recognized, encouraged, supported, and respected by their managers and coworkers everywhere. Teachers will be more committed to the school if the leaders are able to respond to this desire and make their staff feel needed, valuable, competent, and essential.

Managerial and leadership effects on coworkers of the teachers

The inclination to equate leadership with assigned power and status, as well as limiting school authority to the teacher's role, have both been called into question. In schools, teacher leadership has been recommended as a method of distributing leadership. Teacher leadership emphasizes the importance of teachers' contributions to school progress and highlights teachers who have displayed leadership qualities at the same time. This research looked at teacher leadership in public schools in the Philippines using a version of York-Barr and Duke (2004)'s methodology, which related teacher leadership to student learning. It was found that the environment had a crucial part in enabling or restricting teacher leadership practice, and this was taken into account while analyzing the research on the topic. Actions made by teachers who react positively to chances for improvement in teaching and learning are called teacher leadership. This group of educators has a strong sense of moral purpose and the necessary pedagogical and leadership skills. They collaborate with colleagues and the school's administration to establish a learning environment that is conducive to teaching and learning, even in

the face of difficult situations. According to the findings of this research, the country's education reform plan should include recognizing teacher leadership, encouraging teachers to embrace leadership roles, and focusing on professional development programs for both teachers and those in positions of leadership.

There can be no doubt about the relevance of these two ideas in school operations. Today's demands on school administrators and leaders are greater, more severe, and more difficult than ever before. To meet the demands of the school system, it faces a variety of challenges and pressures. A school's survival depends on its ability to quickly deal with and adapt to an ever-changing environment.

There has been an ever-increasing responsibility for all stakeholders as schools and their administration have evolved through time. Students' academic performance will improve, pedagogical procedures will be improved, and communities and public services will be given greater responsibility in the new school environment. Decentralization is necessary to accomplish these goals as well as to increase school autonomy and accountability. In order to suit the educational demands of this century, all of these have been developed.

A teacher contributes to the school's high level of performance by making effective use of the resources available (Lunenburg, 1995). If a teacher is to be regarded as a school administrator, he or she must be knowledgeable, skilled, and capable of promoting the achievement of all students by effectively managing the school's operations and resources.

Many instructors in Asia were not prepared for their new job and function in school administration, according to a research by Popper (2012). Similarly, Albano (2006) found that teachers were more empowered in their administrative roles than in their supervisory roles when she studied secondary teachers' degree of empowerment.

Teachers are the school's administrators and leaders, and they determine the course. They are in charge of the day-to-day running of the school. The enormous shifts in the school's scope, range of abilities, and set of required skills have increased the complexity, diversity, and difficulty of their responsibilities. Teacher leaders and managers have a critical role in a school's vision, purpose and objectives; curriculum and instruction; finance and budgeting; school plant and facilities; student services; and the school improvement plan. Accuracy, efficacy, and efficiency of the school's overall performance are all factors that must be taken into consideration while identifying the competences required by instructors in these areas.

For a classroom to function at its best, a teacher must be motivated to learn and grow in order to improve student outcomes. Schools under constant pressure from a variety of groups with vested interests in the educational process. The school's overall structure is shaped by the abilities of its leaders and management.

Educational leaders are challenged by the demand to improve the leadership and management abilities of teachers as the most powerful individual in supporting reform, change, and innovation in the performance of these activities. There are new possibilities and risks related to the rising changes in leading and managing companies that must be discovered while at the same time harmonizing them with important management practices. The foundations of planning, organizing, leading, and managing remain the same, regardless of changes in the educational environment. They are still important today, although their shape is constantly changing (Sigh, and Rani, 2017).

Leadership and management skills may be cultivated over time by successful instructors. Reflection and self-awareness are essential to completing one's difficulties in order to be efficient and productive in the workplace. Instead of just appointing the ideal individual to a job, schools need to teach that person in the skills necessary to maintain and improve a climate of efficient and successful leadership and management.

Cano and Librado (2010), citing Schartz, identified the following external pressures on school leaders and the learning environment for which no remedy has been provided: Politically, this means new tasks, school programs, and evaluation; economically, this means tighter budgets and restricted expenditures; socially, this means the status and image of teachers; globally, this means inter-school ranking and competition; educationally, this means school efficiency; didactically and methodologically, this means dynamic teaching; and finally, multimedia, this means measuring the effectiveness of teaching.

Many aspects of teaching need the use of a wide variety of management skills and leadership abilities. Schools that encourage student success, lifelong learning, and support school reform and high teaching standards should be included in the list of eligible schools.

Perceptions of Teachers to the Management and Leadership Styles of their respective Teachers

Table 1

Items	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
They encourage my team to participate when it comes decision making time and they try to implement their ideas and suggestions.	2.23	Disagree

Nothing is more important than accomplishing a goal or task.	2.14	Disagree
They closely monitor the schedule to ensure a task or project will be completed in time.	2.10	Disagree
They enjoy coaching people on new tasks and procedures.	2.07	Disagree
The more challenging a task is, the more they enjoy it.	2.34	Disagree
They encourage the employees to be creative about their job.	2.47	Disagree
When seeing a complex task through to completion, they ensure that every detail is accounted for.	2.61	Disagree
They find it easy to carry out several complicated tasks at the same time.	2.11	Disagree
They enjoy reading articles, books, and journals about training, leadership, and psychology; and then putting what they have read into action.	2.17	Disagree
When correcting mistakes, they do not worry about jeopardizing relationships.	2.13	Disagree
TOTAL	2.24	Disagree

Using the data in Table 1, we can see how instructors perceive their teachers' management and leadership approaches. Table 2 results show that teachers' perceptions of their teachers' management and leadership style were associated with their satisfaction with the evaluation system and that, specifically, the more positively they rated their teachers' leadership, the more likely they were to report satisfaction with their evaluation process. However, the overall weighted mean of 2.24 and verbally interpreted as "Disagree" on the Table 1 results. Teachers' satisfaction with the assessment procedure was similarly linked to their evaluation grade.

A study by Jacob (2011) indicated that instructors use information on teacher productivity in their judgments about teacher removal; teachers dismissed lower-performing and more often absent teachers. More successful instructors are more likely to hire better teachers, according to Branch et al. (2012). More effective teachers were recruited, kept, and fired from Miami-Dade Public Schools using school-level value-added indicators, according to Béteille et al. (2009) in their study of Miami-Dade Public Schools. They also discovered some evidence that excellent instructors might help other teachers in their schools improve their own performance.. Instructors like teachers who have a blend of professional and personal attributes, according to Harris et al. (2010), and tenure restrictions may favor less experienced educators.

Table 2
Level of Teacher Work Performance based on Self-Assessment Tool

Domains	Mean (CompetencyLevel)	Verbal Interpretation
Social Regard for Learning	1.58	Developing
Learning Environment	2.08	Developing
Diversity of Learners	2.17	Developing
Curriculum	1.64	Developing
Planning, Assessing and Reporting	1.89	Developing
Community Linkages	1.74	Developing
Personal and Professional Growth	2.84	Experienced
TOTAL	1.99	Developing

According to the Self-Assessment Tool, the current work performance level of teachers is shown in Table 2, with a weighted mean of 1.99 for nearly all domains. Personal and Professional Growth's weighted mean is 2.84, which is read as "Experienced" in the context of the teacher's skills. However, training demands must take precedence over these strengths. The instructor appraises the identified learning requirements while taking into account the school's future growth goals. Teachers need to develop themselves so that they can help the school address the most pressing issues and priorities.

Many studies have shown that instructors have a significant impact on a school's structure, culture, and purpose. It takes the combined efforts of every teacher in a school to build a dynamic and thriving learning environment. The formation of a school learning community relies heavily on the leadership of school teachers in the field of professional development for teachers. Examples of recent U.S. standards adoption include the

National Co-teacher Development Council. Teachers are referred to as crucial participants in the implementation of these standards in schools because of their advocacy, support, and capacity to influence others (NSDC, 2005).

Table 3
Effect of management and leadership of teachers in Terms of Professional Development

Items	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1.1 Heads show excellent charismatic characteristics	2.13	Disagree
1.2 Heads are considered as company role models and an inspiration to the employees	2.47	Disagree
1.3 Heads give consideration to each individual	3.07	Agree
1.4 Headstreat groups and not individually	3.45	Agree
1.5 Heads give opportunities for each individual to improve through intellectual stimulation	3.11	Agree
TOTAL	2.84	Disagree

Table 3 shows the impact of management and leadership on teachers' professional growth. The aggregate weighted mean of 2.84 suggests that they are speaking "Disagree" on the aforementioned things. These guiding principles, according to them, should be implemented by teachers, and the quality of teacher professional development should be improved as a result. There seems to be an issue in the management and leadership styles of the teachers at the school, despite their primary responsibility to develop and maintain a pleasant and healthy teaching and learning environment for everyone, including professional co-teachers.

An important part of the teacher's job is helping individuals within and outside of the school to defrost old ideas about education so that new approaches may be explored. Teachers at the school are aware that a focus on teacher professional development is necessary for school reform and improvement to be effective (Hart & Bredeson, 2006). 'Focusing on people is the most successful strategy to alter any organization,' according to Dufour and Berkey (2005). In truth, only people can be said to undergo transformation in an organization.

Table 4
Significant relationship between the management and leadership style and the teachers work performance and its demographic profile

	Teacher Work Performance	Effects of Management and Leadership Styles	Profiles
Pearson Correlation			
Age	1.000	0.027	.320
Civil Status	0.027	1.000	.264
Gender	.320	.264	1.000
			.387**

Significant (2 tailed)	.	.	.
Age	.841	.841	.235
Civil Status			
Gender	.235	.124	.124

Age, gender, and civil status seem to have no major impact on a teacher's job performance as a result of their management and leadership style. Their profile is unaffected by the aforementioned elements. It takes the combined efforts of every teacher in a school to build a dynamic and thriving learning environment. Teacher leadership is essential to creating and maintaining a school learning community.

Most instructors, like all educators, have their particular areas of specialization in teaching. An ex-teacher of mathematics may have a wealth of knowledge about math education, but they may have little knowledge about how to teach other languages. It is impossible for a teacher to know everything. Teacher leaders can provide the breadth of professional expertise required for long-term school development. Individual teachers have their own specialties, of course. This is why teacher leaders are more important than ever for school development. No teacher can accomplish everything.

Teachers, in their capacity as human capital managers, have the ability to impact student results via the selection of co-teachers. Assistant teachers, school coaches, and assistants might all be hired and fired as part of this process. Involving a co-teacher in the decision-making process might potentially have an impact on the school's performance (Spillane, 2005; Ikemoto, Taliaferro, and Adams, 2012). A teacher's capacity to make 10 of these choices, including non-teaching co-teacher, leadership roles, and shared decision-making, varies by district and state.

Conclusions

When it comes to teachers' leadership styles and their relationship to teaching performance, this study's goal bears similarities and differences with those of other studies in the field of educational leadership, both foreign and domestic. A variety of viewpoints on the responsibilities and functions that construction instructors should fulfill may be found in school leadership and management literature. Becoming a good building manager isn't enough anymore, that's for sure! As a teacher, you must be a psychologist, a social worker and a school facility manager at the same time. You must also be an evaluation expert and an educational visionary at the same time. It's becoming increasingly difficult for them to keep up with the ever-increasing number of responsibilities and demands on their time. School or site-based administration, in addition to decentralizing control, has resulted in a shift in the teacher's role, which has resulted in the transfer of a significant amount of decision-making power from the district office to individual schools. As a result, building instructors' jobs have become more challenging than ever. The researcher conducted a comparative analysis of the findings of this study and those of other relevant studies obtained from across the world. Fullan's examination of leadership styles in other countries focused on five primary characteristics: moral purpose, flexibility, logical skills development, and the ability to maintain consistency in the workplace.

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